

RAISE

RAISE is RESCALE’s dynamic REST API fuzzing component, built on Microsoft’s RESTler and extended with a genetic-algorithm ML layer to prioritize high-risk API paths. It compiles a grammar from the target’s OpenAPI/Swagger spec, then evolves request sequences (selection, crossover, mutation) to uncover bugs and security issues more efficiently. RAISE keeps a history of sequences/responses, includes a garbage collector to clean up created objects, and adds security-tuned bug categorization.

API Security Fuzzing Module (EvoMaster)

The API Security Fuzzing Module builds on EvoMaster, an evolutionary testing framework, to explore and secure RESTful APIs. By combining genetic algorithms with curated payloads from FuzzDB and code coverage analysis, EvoMaster automatically generates, mutates, and evolves test cases that stress APIs far beyond conventional testing. The process is fully automated: the system ingests an API schema, runs EvoMaster to produce diverse test inputs, and reports vulnerabilities and coverage data back to the Orchestrator and DSCG pipeline for integration into the TBOM. Evaluation on both custom APIs and intentionally vulnerable systems confirms its effectiveness for detecting input validation flaws, injection points, and robustness issues in modern API ecosystems.

Dynamic Hardware Analyzer

The Dynamic Hardware Analyzer extends RESCALE’s dynamic testing capabilities into the hardware domain, focusing on detecting vulnerabilities through side-channel leakage assessment. It is designed to evaluate cryptographic IP cores and FPGA-based systems against physical leakage threats such as power consumption or electromagnetic emissions. The tool operates in two stages: a Trace Collector, which gathers leakage traces from hardware sensors or emulated environments, and a Trace Analyzer, which applies statistical and AI-driven techniques; including Correlation/Differential Power Analysis (CPA/DPA), Test Vector Leakage Assessment (TVLA), and machine learning models (e.g., SVM, Random Forest, CNN) — to uncover exploitable information flows.

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